

On the Stability and Electrokinetic Potential of Cadmium Ferrocyanide Sol

Pranab K. Pal and Anil K. Roychowdhury

A purified cadmium ferrocyanide sol in two lots (sol A and sol B) has been prepared to ascertain the relation between stability and electrokinetic potential. The true ζ -potential of sol A for a given slow rate of coagulation has been determined by the electro-osmotic as well as by the electrophoretic methods, using the Smoluchowski equation with correction for surface conductance. The true ζ -potential for a given rapid rate of coagulation of sol A has also been determined by the electro-osmotic method only. The value of the true ζ -potential for rapid coagulation has been found to be slightly less than that for the slow one.

The true electrokinetic potential of sol B for a given rapid rate of coagulation has been evaluated from the electro-osmotic and also the microcataphoretic data.

From the results it is concluded that a given rate of coagulation of the sols is characterised by a definite value of the true ζ -potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used.

Many authors tried to correlate the stability of a colloid with its electrical charge. Experimental results of Powis¹, Mukherjee *et al.*², Kruyt *et al.*³, and Ghosh⁴ on As_2S_3 sol and also of Kruyt *et al.*⁵ and Weiser *et al.*⁶ on AgI sol do not support either Hardy's theory⁷ of coagulation at the isoelectric point or Powis' theory⁸ of coagulation at a critical potential. Hermans⁹, Verwey and Overbeek¹⁰, Rutgers¹¹, and Bikerman¹² have expressed the view that the calculation of ζ -potential from the Smoluchowski equation¹³ may lead to considerable errors.

Rutgers¹¹ has shown that the true zeta-potential, ζ , of a glass-capillary wall of radius r in contact with water or a very dilute electrolyte solution can be found by applying surface conductivity correction, using the equation:

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta SE_s}{DP} \left(1 + \frac{2\kappa}{rS}\right) = \zeta_a \left(1 + \frac{2\kappa}{rS}\right)$$

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 734.
2. *This Journal*, 1928, 5, 735.
3. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 170.
4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2693.
5. *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 78, 32.
6. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 179.
7. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1900, A66, 110.
8. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 89, 186.
9. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 133.
10. "Theory of the Stability of Lyophobic Colloids", 1948.
11. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, 36, 69.
12. *Ibid.*, 1940, 36, 154.
13. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1918, 93, 129.

where E_s represents the streaming potential; P , the pressure used for streaming the liquid through the capillary; α , the specific surface conductance; S , the specific conductance of the liquid in bulk; η , its coefficient of viscosity, D , its dielectric constant, ζ_a being the apparent zeta-potential.

Later on Ghosh¹⁴ derived an expression, which can be written as

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{m}{S} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $m = 3\alpha/a\zeta r$; a represents the phase volume ratio of the liquid to the solid forming the diaphragm; the other terms have the usual significance. According to Ghosh *et al.*¹⁵ a similar expression:

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{m}{S} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

(where $m = \alpha/R\zeta$) for electrophoresis can be found from the equation of Booth¹⁶ and Henry¹⁷ for large values of (κR) and for non-conducting particles, where R is the radius of a particle and κ , the reciprocal of the thickness of the electrical double layer.

The present investigation has been carried out using cadmium ferrocyanide sol with a view to ascertaining its true ζ -potential at known rates of coagulation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Sol.—In measuring the conductance of mixtures of heavy metal salts and potassium ferrocyanide, Britton and Dodd¹⁸ noticed that heavy metal ferrocyanides, viz., Cd, Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Th, etc., became peptised by washing.

The sol was prepared by addition of an $M/5$ cadmium chloride solution to an excess of $M/10$ potassium ferrocyanide solution at a slow rate with constant stirring. The mixture was then dialysed in cellophane bags against distilled water for about 30 days. After dialysis, the sol, designated as sol A, was stored in a clean Jena flask and allowed to age for two weeks. The sol was negatively charged. Its pH was 6.72 and the specific conductance at 25° was 2.38×10^{-4} mho/cm.

Another lot (sol B) was prepared by the same method. Its specific conductance at 25° was 3.10^{-4} mho/cm.

14. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, 49, 1977.

15. *Nature*, 1955, 176, 1061.

16. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 44, 955.

17. *Ibid.*, 1948, 44, 1021.

18. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1543.

Equicoagulating Concentrations of Electrolytes

The concentrations of different electrolytes, which coagulate the colloids at a given rate, have been termed as the equicoagulating concentrations.

(a). *Rapid Rate of Coagulation*.—A definite volume of the sol (2 ml) was mixed with the same volume of an electrolyte solution of the desired concentration in a test tube and the mixture was kept in a stand under observation for 10 minutes, avoiding any unnecessary jerking. At the end of 10 minutes, the tube was centrifuged exactly for 2 minutes at a definite speed. The supernatant liquid from the top was taken in a clean dry test tube and examined for transparency. The concentration of an electrolyte, which produces just clear supernatant solution by the above treatment, is taken as its equicoagulating concentration. The electrolytes used for sol A were KCl, BaCl₂, and mixtures of KCl and BaCl₂. For sol B, the electrolytes used were KCl, MgCl₂, La(NO₃)₃, and mixtures of KCl-MgCl₂ and KCl-La(NO₃)₃.

(b). *Slow Rate of Coagulation*.—The equicoagulating concentration of electrolytes for a slow rate of coagulation was also determined for sol A in the same way as described for the rapid coagulation. The mixture after keeping undisturbed for 48 hours was centrifuged for 2 min. at a definite speed and the transparency of the supernatant liquid was examined. The electrolytes used were KCl, BaCl₂, AlCl₃, and mixtures of KCl-BaCl₂ and BaCl₂-AlCl₃.

Electro-osmotic Experiments with Sol A at 25°.—A given volume (40 ml) of the sol was mixed with an equal volume of the electrolyte of the desired concentration and the mixture was allowed to stand for 48 hours for slow and 10 minutes for rapid rate of coagulation. The coagula were separated from the supernatant solutions by centrifuging at a given speed. The entire coagula were then transferred to a U-tube and a diaphragm was made therein by centrifuging the system at a suitable speed. For a particular set of experiments, the volume of the diaphragm within the U-tube was maintained the same by adjusting its time of rotation. This ensured constancy in the value of 'm', assuming that κ remained constant at the equicoagulating point. The U-tube containing the diaphragm was filled with the supernatant liquid and the electro-osmotic velocity was measured by the moving air-bubble method of Mukherjee *et al.*¹⁹.

Electrophoretic Experiments with Sol A at 25°.—These experiments were performed in a modified form of Burton's U-tube apparatus²⁰. The sol (20 ml) was mixed with the electrolyte of equicoagulating concentration, allowed to attain equilibrium for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., and then centrifuged at a given speed for 2 min. to remove coarser particles. The mixture of colloid and electrolyte was then used as the lower liquid in the U-tube. The solution filling the upper part of the U-tube was prepared previously by mixing 100 ml of sol with 100 ml of electrolyte of proper concentration and removing the colloidal particles by centrifuging after 48 hours. Reversible Ag/AgCl electrodes were used and the electrolytes selected contained Cl⁻ as anion.

The distance moved by the colloid-liquid boundary under a given current in a

19. This *Journal*, 1927, 4, 493.

20. Ghosh *et al.*, *Kolloid Z.*, 1958, 158, 45.

definite time was measured. The mean value of the upward and downward movements of the boundary was taken for the calculation of ζ_p by the Smoluchowski equation.

Electro-osmotic Experiments with Sol B at 25°.—The same procedure, as described previously for sol A, was followed with sol B to evaluate the values of ζ_a at the equicoagulating concentrations of the electrolytes used in the region of rapid coagulation.

Microcataphoretic Experiments with Sol B at 25°.—The mobility of the colloidal particles was determined by means of a microcataphoretic apparatus, described by Chakravarti and Ghosh²¹. The microscope with which the particles were observed in the cell carried a micrometer scale in the eye piece. With the help of the scale, particles of the desired size could be selected very easily. The average time taken to cover a given distance for direct and reverse motion was used for calculation.

FIG. 1

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 represents, for sol A, the plot of $1/\zeta_a$ against $1/S$ at the equicoagulating concentrations of the electrolytes used. It will be observed that the plot in each case provides a straight line in agreement with the equation of Ghosh⁴. For the rapid rate, the values of ζ_a

vary from 15.2 to 24.0 mv and the true ζ , obtained from the intercept on $1/\zeta_a$ axis, is 27.8 mv (vide curve a). For the slow coagulation, the values of ζ_a , obtained from electro-osmotic measurements, vary from 18.1 to 26.2 mv and the true value of ζ is found to be 31.8 mv (vide curve b). The same value, 31.8 mv, of true ζ is also found by the electrophoretic method. The values of ζ_a in this case vary from 27.8 to 30.6 mv (vide curve c). It may therefore be concluded that the agreement between the values of true zeta-potential obtained by the two methods is quite satisfactory and the value of 31.8 mv may be taken to represent the true ζ -potential of the cadmium ferrocyanide sol A in the zone of slow coagulation investigated.

For the rapid rate, the results of electro-osmotic and microcataphoretic experiments with sol B have been represented in Fig. 2. The electro-osmotic and microcataphoretic

FIG. 2

values of ζ_a vary from 15.8 to 27.4 mv. Here also the agreement between the two methods is very satisfactory. Moreover, it should be noted that at the rapid rate of coagulation, the values of true ζ for sol A and sol B are 27.8 mv and 27.4 mv respectively, which are very close to each other. This may be accidental or due to following the same method of preparation.

It may be pointed out that for sol A, as the time required for coagulation varies from 10 minutes to 48 hours, the true ζ -potential also varies from 27.8 mv to 31.8 mv. Since the difference is not much, we may conclude that a critical zone of electrokinetic potential exists for any observable coagulation of cadmium ferrocyanide sol to occur by the addition of electrolytes.

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